

LEXICAL SEMANTIC APPROACHES TO PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Lexical semantic approaches to phraseological units provide valuable insights into the meaning, interpretation, and usage of these fixed expressions within a linguistic framework. This section explores some of the prominent lexical semantic approaches, highlighting their contributions to the study of phraseological units.

Collocational Approaches:

Collocational approaches examine the regular co-occurrence patterns of words within phraseological units. They focus on the relationship between the components of a phraseological unit and their combinatory possibilities. According to Firth (1957)¹, collocations are "the habitual juxtaposition of a particular word with others." These approaches aim to uncover the inherent semantic associations and constraints that govern the selection and combination of words within phraseological units.

One influential collocational framework is Sinclair's theory of idiom principle (Sinclair, 1991)². Sinclair argues that phraseological units are conventionalized collocations with a unique semantic and syntactic behavior. He emphasizes the significance of the whole phrase and its indivisibility, suggesting that phraseological units have an idiomatic character beyond the sum of their individual components.

Semantic Decomposition Approaches:

Semantic decomposition approaches aim to analyze the meaning of phraseological units by breaking them down into their component parts. This involves examining the literal meanings of the constituent words and exploring how they contribute to the overall meaning of the phraseological unit. These approaches consider both the literal and figurative interpretations of phraseological units.

One notable framework is the Decompositional Analysis of Idioms (Gibbs, 1994)³, which proposes a systematic process to identify the literal and figurative aspects of idiomatic expressions. This approach analyzes the lexical, syntactic, and semantic properties of phraseological units to uncover the underlying conceptual metaphors or metonymies that contribute to their figurative meanings.

Prototype-based Approaches:

Prototype-based approaches consider phraseological units as instances of prototypical configurations within a semantic category. These approaches focus on identifying the central or prototypical instances of a phraseological unit and examining how other related expressions deviate from or conform to that prototype. Prototype-based analyses shed light on the variation and flexibility observed in the use and interpretation of phraseological units.

Langacker's Cognitive Grammar framework (Langacker, 1987)⁴ offers a prototype-based perspective on phraseological units. It suggests that phraseological units have both a central

¹ Firth, J. R. (1957). *Papers in Linguistics 1934-1951*. Oxford University Press.

² Sinclair, J. M. (1991). *Corpus, Concordance, Collocation*. Oxford University Press.

³ Gibbs, R. W. (1994). *The Poetics of Mind: Figurative Thought, Language, and Understanding*. Cambridge University Press.

⁴ Langacker, R. W. (1987). *Foundations of Cognitive Grammar: Theoretical Prerequisites*. Stanford University Press.

meaning and a range of peripheral meanings, allowing for variation and contextual adaptation. This approach emphasizes the cognitive processes involved in comprehending and producing phraseological units.

Frame-based Approaches:

Frame-based approaches view phraseological units as language expressions that evoke cognitive frames or mental structures. Frames represent knowledge structures that organize and guide our understanding of specific concepts or domains. Phraseological units can activate these frames, triggering specific associations and expectations in the interpretation process.

Fillmore's Frame Semantics (Fillmore, 1982)⁵ provides a frame-based perspective on phraseological units. This approach identifies the underlying frames evoked by phraseological units and examines how these frames shape the interpretation and use of these expressions in communication. Frame-based analyses offer insights into the contextual and inferential aspects of phraseological units.

These lexical semantic approaches contribute to our understanding of phraseological units by exploring their meaning, usage, and cognitive aspects. By examining collocational patterns, decomposing meanings, considering prototypes, and analyzing cognitive frames, these approaches provide a rich framework for investigating the semantic properties and interpretation of phraseological units in a scientific and systematic manner.

Corpus linguistics and computational methods play a crucial role in studying the semantic features of phraseological units. These approaches provide valuable tools and techniques for collecting, analyzing, and interpreting large amounts of linguistic data, enabling researchers to uncover the semantic properties of phraseological units in a systematic and empirical manner. Here are some ways in which corpus linguistics and computational methods contribute to the study of phraseological units' semantic features:

Data Collection:

Corpus linguistics allows researchers to collect extensive and diverse linguistic data, including naturally occurring language samples that contain phraseological units. Corpus-based studies provide access to large collections of texts, speeches, or other forms of discourse, ensuring a representative sample for analysis. By utilizing corpora, researchers can examine the occurrence, frequency, and distribution of phraseological units in different contexts, genres, and registers.

Collocational Analysis:

Computational methods facilitate collocational analysis, which is crucial for understanding the semantic features of phraseological units. By analyzing the co-occurrence patterns of words within a corpus, researchers can identify the most frequent collocates associated with specific phraseological units. This information helps uncover the semantic associations and constraints that govern the use of phraseological units, shedding light on their lexical and syntactic properties.

Semantic Relations and Associations:

Corpus linguistics enables the exploration of semantic relations and associations between phraseological units and other lexical items in a language. By analyzing the concordance lines, co-occurrence patterns, and collocational profiles of phraseological units, researchers can

⁵ Fillmore, C. J. (1982). Frame Semantics. In *Linguistics in the Morning Calm* (pp. 111-137).

identify the semantic fields, thematic domains, and conceptual networks to which these expressions belong. This allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the semantic features and contextual usage of phraseological units.

Semantic Variation and Change:

Corpus-based studies enable the investigation of semantic variation and change in phraseological units over time and across different registers or genres. By examining historical corpora or diachronic data, researchers can track the evolution of phraseological units, uncovering shifts in their semantic associations, metaphorical extensions, or changes in their collocational patterns. Corpus linguistics provides a valuable resource for studying the dynamic nature of phraseological units' semantics.

Computational Analysis and Statistical Modeling:

Computational methods, including statistical modeling and machine learning techniques, allow researchers to extract and analyze linguistic patterns from large corpora. These methods can be employed to identify significant collocations, measure the strength of word associations, or classify phraseological units based on their semantic properties. Computational approaches provide quantitative evidence and statistical insights into the semantic features and usage patterns of phraseological units.

The combination of corpus linguistics and computational methods offers a powerful approach to studying the semantic features of phraseological units. These methodologies provide researchers with access to vast amounts of linguistic data, enabling the exploration of semantic relations, collocational patterns, and variation in phraseological units' meanings. The systematic and data-driven nature of these approaches enhances our understanding of the rich and complex semantic landscape of phraseological units in language.

References:

1. Langacker, R. W. (1987). *Foundations of Cognitive Grammar: Theoretical Prerequisites*. Stanford University Press.
2. Fillmore, C. J. (1982). Frame Semantics. In *Linguistics in the Morning Calm* (pp. 111-137).
3. Partington, A. (2013). Corpora and discourse: A most congruous beast. In *The Oxford handbook of corpus linguistics* (pp. 289-302). Oxford University Press.
4. McEnery, T., & Hardie, A. (2011). *Corpus linguistics: Method, theory and practice*. Cambridge University Press.
5. Rayson, P. (2008). From key words to key semantic domains. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics*, 13(4), 519-549.
6. Wodak, R., & Meyer, M. (Eds.). (2009). *Methods of critical discourse analysis*. Sage Publications.
7. <https://www.english-corpora.org/coca/>
8. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/>
9. <https://www.linguisticsociety.org/>